

EMERGENCIES TREATMENT FOR TONGUE LACERATION IN CHILDREN : A SERIAL CASE

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In children, tongue laceration may occur through several mechanisms, but are most common after a fall or a collision with an object or person. Tongue laceration provides a challenge for an emergency physician with a thought to suture or not. Wound closure typically involves local anaesthesia, sedative drugs, or even general anaesthesia. **Objective:** To describe emergencies treatment and adequate wound closure for tongue laceration in children. **Case Report:** Three cases of tongue laceration on the child's in the Emergency Unit, Hasan Sadikin Hospital and Padjadjaran University Dental Hospital, with a complaint of bleeding from the tongue due to fall and collision with toys. Clinical examination shows tongue laceration with different location and size. The first case was laceration of the dorsal and ventral of the tongue with 4x1 cm and 2x1x1 cm in size, wound closure and debridement were performed under general anaesthesia in the operating room. The second case was laceration of the dorsal tongue with 3x0.5x0.5 cm in size, wound closure and debridement was performed with sedative drugs and the third case was laceration of the anterior tongue with 3x1x1 cm in size, wound closure and debridement was performed in local anaesthesia. Furthermore, analgesics, antibiotic and antitetanus injection are given. **Discussion:** The treatment of tongue laceration should consider signs and symptoms of airway obstruction, uncontrolled bleeding, extensive tearing and cooperative levels in patients. Management of tongue laceration in children is performed wound cleansing, tongue muscle and mucosa suturing under local anaesthesia in fairly cooperative patients and with sedative drugs and general anaesthesia in uncooperative patients. **Conclusion:** The treatment for tongue laceration in children requires special treatment consider the level of cooperative in children and the large of the wound, which can be performed under local, sedative drugs and general anaesthesia.

KEYWORDS Emergency, Tongue laceration, Child

Introduction

Injuries to the tongue are often treated in the emergency department or other acute care settings. Falls, contact injuries, and child

abuse are common causes of injury to the mouth. In children, tongue laceration may occur through any of these mechanisms but are most common after a fall or a collision with an object or person in the home. The decision of whether or not to repair a tongue laceration is controversial. The literature offers vague and conflicting recommendations. On the one hand, because of the rich vascular supply, most tongue lacerations heal rapidly without intervention. On the other hand, the tongue plays a crucial role in speech and swallowing, and poor outcomes may compromise these functions. Tongue lacerations in which poor healing may compromise tongue function require more aggressive treatment. [1,2]

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Tongue laceration provides a challenge for an emergency physician with a thought to suture or not to suture because the behaviour of paediatric patients is a major consideration. Traditional wound closure typically involves local anaesthesia, sedative drugs, or even general anaesthesia, which are time-consuming and some of them are often anxiety provoking for surgeons, patients and their parents and are also associated with other complications. [3,4]

Paediatric tongue laceration possesses a dilemma to the operating surgeon to suture, not to suture or any alternative manner to approximate the wounds. Wound closure is a part of any surgical procedure, and the objective of laceration repair or incision closure is to approximate edge of the wound so the natural healing process may occur. [4]

The aim of this serial case to describe emergencies treatment and adequate wound closure for tongue laceration in children.

Case Report

Case 1

A 4-year-old boy presented to Hasan Sadikin Hospital Emergency Departement with a chief complaint of pain and bleeding from the tongue after he was playing at the top of a truck, suddenly he fell with mechanism his mouth hit the floor of truck about 7 hours before admission. On general examination, the patient was conscious, uncooperative, no history of loss of consciousness, vomiting, seizures, ear, nose and throat bleed, or injury to other parts of the body. History of immunization was complete from the primary survey and secondary survey within normal limit. An extraoral examination revealed symmetrical face and oedema at upper lip region.

Figure 1. Extraoral presentation with symmetrical face and oedema at upper lip region.

An Intraoral examination revealed mouth opening to be 3 cm, a laceration over dorsum penetrated to ventral of the tongue with 4x1 cm in size, irregular edge, at 2/3 anterior of the dorsum of the tongue with 2x1x1 cm in size, irregular edge with muscle based and avulsion of teeth 51,61. There was no active bleeding, but the gaping nature of the wound made us to reapproximate it.

Management of this patient in the emergency room, at the time of entry, is done early clinical examination because the history of the trauma mechanism obtained falling from a height so that controlled bleeding to secure the airway and installation of c-spine control to prevent the existence of more severe trauma. Patients then performed the infusion of electrolyte. Further examination continued of the primary survey and secondary survey as other trauma patients.

After ensuring no other trauma, an intraoral examination was performed to determine the location and extent of injury to

Figure 2. Intraoral presentation of multiple lacerations of the tongue.

the patient tongue where the patient found extensive wound on the tongue and uncooperative patient; it was decided to perform wound closure in general anaesthesia in the operation room. The need for repair and accompanying risk and complication of procedural under general anaesthesia was also explained. However, the patient's parent was willing for the above treatment, so we took written consent from his parents.

Patients then performed preparations with support examination in the form of a complete blood count and radiological examination of chest, cervical, and head x-ray with the result within normal limit. Afterwards, the patient is consult to paediatric and anaesthesia department for preparation of feasibility of action in general anaesthesia.

Figure 3. Radiological examination presentation within normal limit

The patient was injected antitetanus serum and given medication therapy of ampicillin injection 375 mg and ketorolac injection 30mg intravenous as well as wound debridement and wound closure with suturing under general anaesthesia in the operating room. Wound debridement was performed with gauge and irrigation with NaCl 0.9% solution, then suturing at the muscle of tongue with horizontal mattress suture and the superficial with simple interrupted suture using chromic sutures sizes 4.0. Patient was hospitalized two days for observation was given medication therapy ampicillin inj 4 x 375 mg 0.75 IV, dexamethasone inj 2 x mg, paracetamol Syr 3x120 mg and kaltrofen Supp 2 x 1 and sent home with improvement and was given medication amoxicillin syrup 3x180 mg, paracetamol syrup 3x180 mg and education his parents for keep the cleanliness around the wound.

Figure 4. Intraoral presentation of post-treatment.

Case 2

An 11-month-old baby boy presented to Padjadjaran Dental University Hospital Emergency Departement with a chief complaint of pain and bleeding from the tongue after a self-fall in his residence about 3 hours before admission. The patient underwent cleft lip surgery at Unpad Dental Hospital 8 months ago. On general examination, the patient was conscious, uncooperative, no history of loss of consciousness, seizures, ear, nose and throat bleed, or injury to other parts of the body from the primary survey and secondary survey within normal limit. An extraoral examination revealed the symmetrical face and scar post cleft lip surgery.

Figure 5. Extraoral presentation of symmetrical face and scar post cleft lip surgery.

An Intraoral examination revealed mouth opening to be 3 cm, a laceration over the dorsum of the tongue with 3x0.5x0.5cm in size, irregular edge and muscle based. There was no active bleeding, but the gaping nature of the wound made us to reapproximate it.

Figure 6. Intraoral presentation of laceration at the dorsum of the tongue.

Because of the age of the patient, size of the wound, and uncooperative, so wound closure was a plan to perform under general anaesthesia. The need for repair and accompanying risk and complication of general procedural anaesthesia was also explained. However, the patient's parent was not willing for the above treatment. So an alternative modality of wound closure with sedative drugs and local anaesthesia, then the parents were informed about the complication related to it, but child's parent was willing for this treatment modality, so we took written consent from his parents

The patient was given medication therapy of amoxicillin syrup 180 mg, paracetamol syrup 180 mg and diazepam sup

5mg as well as wound debridement and wound closure with sedative drugs and local anaesthesia with local infiltration of the wound using lidocaine. Wound debridement was performed with gauge and irrigation with NaCl 0.9% solution, then suturing at the muscle of tongue with horizontal mattress suture and the superficial with simple interrupted suture using chromic sutures sizes 4.0. Patient sent home with improvement and was given medication amoxicillin syrup 3 x 180 mg, and paracetamol syrup 3x 180 mg and education his parents for keeping the cleanliness around the wound.

Figure 7. Intraoral presentation of post treatment.

Case 3

A 2.5-year-old boy presented to Hasan Sadikin Hospital Emergency Departement with a chief complaint of pain and bleeding from the tongue after he was playing with a toys stick, suddenly he fell and collision with his toys about 4 hours before admission. On general examination, the patient was conscious, cooperative, well oriented to place, person and situation, no history of loss of consciousness, seizures, ear, nose and throat bleed, or injury to other parts of the body. History of immunization was complete From the primary survey and secondary survey within normal limit. An extraoral examination revealed the symmetrical face.

Figure 8. Extraoral presentation with a symmetrical face.

An Intraoral examination revealed mouth opening to be 3 cm, a laceration at anterior of the tongue with 2x1x1 cm in size, irregular edge and muscle based. There was no active bleeding, but the gaping nature of the wound made us to reapproximate it.

In the emergency room, the patient was performed routine blood count that show results within normal limit and injection of antitetanus serum. The patient was given medication therapy of amoxicillin syrup 180 mg and paracetamol syrup 180 mg, as well as wound debridement and wound closure with suturing under local anaesthesia with local infiltration of the wound using lidocaine. Wound debridement was performed with gauge and irrigation with NaCl 0.9% solution, then suturing at the muscle of tongue with horizontal mattress suture and the superficial

Figure 9. Intraoral presentation of laceration at anterior of the tongue

with simple interrupted suture using chromic sutures sizes 4.0. Patient sent home with improvement and was given medication Amoxicillin syrup 3x180 mg, and paracetamol syrup 3x180 mg and education his parents to keep the cleanliness around the wound.

Figure 10. Intraoral presentation of post-treatment.

Discussion

The tongue is a muscular organ that sits on the floor of the oropharynx. It is enveloped by mucosa and contains glands, sensory organs, and four pairs of extrinsic muscles. The tongue is essential for several important functions, including normal articulation of the jaw, taste, manipulation of food, swallowing, and the production of normal speech. The tongue has a rich blood supply, and injuries to the tongue or the floor of the mouth may cause serious haemorrhage that potentially threatens the airway. The airway may become compromised sometime after trauma to the tongue or lacerations of the floor of the mouth if veins are damaged, resulting in swelling of the tongue into the oropharynx. Haemorrhage and disfigurement are the two most common concerns in these injuries, although the loss of function, infection, and swelling that compromises the airway are also mentioned as sequelae.[5,6]

As in all trauma patients, the initial clinical assessment should provide rapid identification of potentially fatal conditions. Evaluation for airway compromise, impaired respiratory mechanics, hemorrhagic shock, and altered level of consciousness should be made on arrival at the emergency department. Such system-

atic evaluation helps ensure the detection of potentially serious injuries. The approach to the injured child is discussed in detail separately. Large lacerations may lead to haemorrhage that can potentially threaten the airway and cause hypovolemia. The airway should be evaluated and secured if compromised. Cervical spine immobilization must be maintained in patients in whom cervical spine injury has not been excluded. Determination of the mechanism of injury is crucial in the evaluation of children with tongue lacerations and potentially serious occult injury (e.g., cervical spine injury). This is particularly important in children with high-impact trauma (e.g., motor vehicle accidents, falls from height, direct blows to the face). Because the tongue is highly vascularized, bleeding caused by laceration may distract attention from the more serious injury. Also, information regarding the child's past medical history, including tetanus immunization status, medications, and allergies, should be sought.[2,7]

A tongue laceration in a child poses a management dilemma for the clinician to as suture or not, especially in a young child when behaviour management is an additional consideration. The dilemma is compounded because sedation or even general anesthesia may be required. Tongue laceration are anxiety-provoking injuries for the patient and provider and, in the case of injured children, the parent as well. Closure usually requires some degree of sedation and analgesia and is painful if these measures are not taken. [3,4]

An evaluation of the child's cooperative potential is essential for treatment planning. No single assessment method or tool is completely accurate in predicting a patient's behaviour, but awareness of the multiple influences on a child's response to care can aid in treatment planning. Initially, information can be gathered from the parent through questions regarding the child's cognitive level, temperament/personality characteristics, anxiety and fear, reaction to strangers and behaviour at previous medical/dental visits, as well as how the parent anticipates the child will respond to future treatment. Later, the physician can evaluate cooperative potential by observation of and interaction with the patient. Whether the child is approachable, somewhat shy, or shy and withdrawn may influence the success of various communicative techniques. Assessing the child's development, past experiences, and current emotional state allows the physician to develop a behaviour guidance plan to accomplish the necessary oral health care. During the delivery of care, the physician must remain attentive to the physical and emotional indicators of stress. Changes in adaptive behaviours may require alterations to the behavioural treatment plan.[8]

One of the more reliable and frequently used cooperative rating systems in both clinical and research is the Frankl Scale. This scale separates observed behaviours into four categories ranging from definitely negative to positive. [8]

The decision whether or not to repair the laceration depends upon the extent of the laceration and the risk of compromised function after healing, but evidence suggests that outcomes for most tongue lacerations in young children are not improved by suturing. Lacerations that should be considered for repair include large lacerations (>1 cm in length) that extend into the muscular layers or pass completely through the tongue, deep lacerations on the lateral border of the tongue, large flaps or gaps in the tongue, lacerations with significant hemorrhage, and lacerations that may cause dysfunction if healed improperly (anterior split tongue). Lacerations that do not need repair include lacerations <1 cm in length, non-gaping lacerations, and

Table 1 Frankl Behavioral Rating Scale.

1	--	Negative. Refusal of treatment, forceful crying, fearfulness, or any other overt evidence of extreme negativism.
2	-	Negative. Reluctance to accept treatment, uncooperative, some evidence of negative attitude but not pronounced (sullen, withdrawn).
3	+	Positive. Acceptance of treatment; cautious behaviour at times; willingness to comply with the dentist, at times with reservation, but patient follows the dentist's directions cooperatively.
4	++	Positive. Good rapport with the dentist, interest in the dental procedures, laughter and enjoyment

lacerations assessed to be minor in the clinical judgment of the examiner. [2,7]

The tongue has a rich vascular supply; primary healing occurs once the two lacerated edges are approximated under local anaesthesia, sedative drugs, or general anaesthesia. The need to diagnose and treat, as well as the safety of the patient, practitioner, and staff, should be considered for the use of general anaesthesia. Sedation is indicated for fearful, anxious patients for whom basic behaviour guidance techniques have not been successful, patients who cannot cooperate due to a lack of psychological or emotional maturity and/or mental, physical, or medical disability; and patients for whom the use of sedation may protect the developing psyche and/or reduce medical risk. General anaesthesia is used to help ensure the safety, health, comfort of children undergoing procedures, and indicated for patients who cannot cooperate due to a lack of psychological or emotional maturity and or mental, physical, or medical disability, patients for whom local anaesthesia is ineffective because of acute infection, anatomic variations, or allergy, the extremely uncooperative, fearful, anxious, or uncommunicative child or adolescent, patients requiring significant surgical procedures, and patients for whom the use of general anaesthesia may protect the developing psyche and/or reduce medical risk. [3,8]

The most commonly used method for closing a lacerated tongue wound is suturing. It has various advantages like careful closure, good tissue approximation, highest resilient strength, lowest dehiscent rate. Wound closure is a part of any surgical procedure. The purpose of all wound closure is to approximate the wound edge to facilitate the natural process of uneventful healing for favourable cosmetic and functions. Approximation of paediatric tongue laceration requires prompt judgement skill. The most common location for tongue laceration is in the anterior dorsum of the tongue; the next common location is mid-dorsum and anterior ventral. [4]

Treatment principles for tongue laceration include cleansing of the wound, removal of foreign bodies and suturing of the dorsal and ventral aspects of the lesion. After administration of anaesthesia (local, regional or general) foreign bodies are retrieved as, it is imperative to prevent infection and scar formation the wound cleaned with saline, and the wound sutured tightly. Administer antibiotics if indicated. Suture removal after 4-5 days for lateral border wounds buried resorbable sutures are sometimes indicated to approximate the wound edges and relieve tension on the mucosal sutures.[5]

Tongue lacerations should be repaired with absorbable 3-0 or 4-0-suture material (chromic gut or Vicryl). Particularly deep lacerations may require a two- or three-layered closure to prevent the formation of a hematoma. The deep muscle should be sutured first, followed by the submucosa and mucosa. Full-thickness bites of the mucosal surface and the lingual muscle should be taken to prevent dehiscence. Large tongue lacerations or lacerations involving the lateral border of the tongue should be well approximated, and care should be taken not to overlap tissues. Tetanus prophylaxis may be indicated for dirty wounds and should be considered in children who have avulsed teeth, deep lacerations, or intrusion injuries. [2]

Administration of antibiotic and analgesics if required, oral hygiene instruction should be given as chances of infection are utmost due to oral microflora. It was studied that suturing a tongue laceration does not improve the outcomes or morbidity associated with the type of injury. The oral cavity is bathed in bacteria-rich secretions, as well as food and other foreign material. Previous studies have reported infection rates for lacerations to the oral cavity (including tongue, lips, and mucosa) between 4.3 and 23.1%, which is higher than the overall infection rate of 7.2% for traumatic wounds. It seems logical that this high-risk environment would necessitate the use of prophylactic antibiotics.[3,9]

The post-emergency department care of tongue lacerations, whether or not they are closed primarily, involves maintenance of good oral hygiene, ingestion of a soft diet, prevention of swelling, and monitoring the wound for signs of infection.[2]

Andreasen suggest suturing both dorsum and lateral border injuries. Powers et al. suggest loosely suturing tongue wounds and placing deep sutures in layers. Donat at al. recommends suturing only wounds larger than 2 cm or when hemorrhage is a concern. English agrees that small laceration need not be sutured when wound margins are in good approximation. Toulukian warns that suturing may predispose to invasive, closed space infection.Lamell et al. recommend suturing tongue lacerations if they are gaping at rest, or if they involve the lateral border or if there is active haemorrhaging. He noted on examination that many of the tongue lacerations had well-approximated margins which stopped haemorrhaging, suggesting these injuries to be self-limiting. The goals of laceration repair of the tongue are to attain adequate closure, minimize complications, preserve mobility, and optimize articulation and deglutition. [10]

In this serial case, all of the case when the patient was con-

trolled revealed adequate wound closure of the tongue, no complication and still essential for several important functions, including normal articulation of the jaw, taste, manipulation of food, swallowing, good mobility, and the production of normal speech.

Conclusion

The treatment for tongue laceration in children requires special treatment consider the level of cooperative in children and the size of the wound, which can be performed under local, sedative drugs, and general anaesthesia. Tongue Laceration provides a challenge for an emergency physician with a thought to suture or not to suture, because the behaviour of paediatric patients is a major consideration. Traditional wound closure typically involves local anaesthesia, sedative drugs, or even general anaesthesia, which are time consuming and some of them are often anxiety provoking for surgeons, patients and their parents and are also associated with other complications.

In this serial case, the decision to wound closure with suturing of all cases because the laceration was indicated for suturing, one case performed under general anaesthesia, sedative drugs, and local anaesthesia consider the level of cooperative in children. The established therapies provide effective and adequate wound closure and healing results.

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Competing Interests

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